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"WHAT YOU WRITE IS YOUR HAPPINESS"

Oygul Nematova

Student

Faculty of first English

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Abstract: *Alexander Feinberg's perspective and speech are discussed in this article. On his mind, their journey from Siberia to Tashkent: "I think they moved here to give birth to me." "You can find information about the conversation between Alexander Feinberg and Anastasia Pavlinko. In addition to this, his one statement was chosen as article's title. As a result, I give an advice that you read this article, and I hope that you really like it and gain profit from it.*

Key words: *Alexander Feinberg, translation studies, international literature, development of the Motherland, Uzbek literature, independence, authors' alley, lyrics, national language.*

It is really known that Alexander Feinberg was born on November 2, 1939 in Tashkent. The atrocities of so-called mass repression did not spare his family.

In his prose "My hometown is Tashkent," he declares: "I visited the Russian capital. Here it is. Moscow appears as if it is on my palm. From the window of the eighteenth floor, I look at the history of this city on the horizon and I am overwhelmed. Disappointment! During the revolution, this city threw my single mother on the threshold of Magadan. Many years later, only Tashkent embraced her and warmed her body in the 50-degree cold. "

With the infinite grace and mercy of fate, the poet benefited the friendliness and generosity of the Uzbek people, whose hearts are as warm as the sun, tolerant and kind. We heard over and over again that he would have died before he was born if his family had not met Uzbeks. Anastasia Alexandrovna, the poet's mother, was born in Moscow, while Arkady Lvovich, the poet's father, was born in Gatchina, not far from Peter's. He does, however, explain their journey from Siberia to Tashkent: "I think they moved here to give birth to me."

When we discuss the poet's personality, of course, we must remember the conversation with Anastasia Pavlinko. And the conversation began with the question of

whether the fans could not fit into the stadiums during the meetings with the poets of the sixties of the last century. The author gently explained: "Poetry is not for stadiums at all. For stadiums - sports. Poetry is the destiny of those who dedicate themselves to literature. If you have a book of poetry like this, read it with an inner need dependent on your mood and state of mind. This is the situation when it comes to the problem of relevancy. Poetry, fine arts, music, etc. Any art is always relevant, if it is real.

After receiving a complete response to her query, Anastasia Pavlinko moved on to the topic of how to educate youngsters to read books. The poet's response was fascinating; he stated in his speech that reading interest is better not only in school, but also in kindergarten. What lessons should a youngster be given to encourage him or her to pursue self-education? This was an excellent rhetorical question. In his speech, he stated that the state ensures that young people receive enough education by building new schools, secondary special and higher education institutions, and entrusting the remainder to trained professionals. This is an issue that educators must tackle.

What is the definition of true poetry? The poet responded to this question by saying: "It must touch the heart and enthrall the soul. Unfortunately, individuals who grasp this fundamental reality are few and far between. If you have a little expertise, you can swiftly rhyme words - go ahead, they think. However, this isn't really poetry. Like persons with graphomania, I can write endless amounts of work. Furthermore, there are many young individuals suffering from this ailment who are gradually cooling off from the "creation of works" of poetry. Poetry is like a sudden bright flash that enriches the heart. It's pointless to feel inspired in every situation."

"Have you ever had a hard time finding a rhyme?" Anastasia Pavlinko inquired. Are you looking for a word to describe Marina Svetayeva? I don't have any issues with rhyming. I'll write if I feel like it. But it isn't always the case for me. I may go three or four years without writing a single word of poetry, or I can compose half a book in a week. True enjoyment comes from not knowing what will happen in the second half of a line. Then the second line follows. Marina Svetayeva is an outstanding poet. Another renowned poet who resided in Tashkent during World War II was Anna Akhmatovna.

Alisher Navoi's ghazals have been translated into Russian by many poets. However, not all translations were satisfactory. The translations of M. Derzhavin, S. Ivanov and others are aesthetically much shallower and farther from Navoi's poetry. The poet's creativity is higher than they think. They understand that Alisher Navoi's poetry consists only of hymns of fairies and hurries. We know that Alisher Navoi was Feinberg's favorite poet, that Alisher Navoi had many poems translated by him in his collection of works

published in Russian, that he was happy to have such an honor, and that he had now studied the whole work of this great poet.

When we hear the poet's description of the Sultan of the realm of words, we feel an involuntary sense of pride. If you start to feel Alisher Navoi's work more deeply and subtly, you will realize that it is very deep and multifaceted. The poet expressed many of his thoughts in figurative expressions and symbols. After all, the environment in which he lived was not limited to friends. It amazes me that in those days, there was no one who could only make art, who was limited to only one field in life. For example, Alisher Navoi was a scientist, musicologist, poet, and statesman. He dedicated his work in all spheres to the interests of the people and the well-being of the people.

And finally, I would like to conclude with the words of the poet: "What you write is your happiness, and the publication of your works is your holiday." That is why the simple poet is very happy that poetry evenings are attended by readers of all ages, from schoolchildren to the elderly. Well, their number is small, but the poet was always grateful for their presence.

REFERENCES:

1. Alexander Fainberg “An Attempt to Autobiography”
2. Mikhail Knizhnik “Living Poet” Published in The Jerusalem Journal. Number 31, 2009
3. Musurmonov R. "The Alley of Writers - the Garden of Enlightenment". –T .: Uzbek literature and art, June 19, 2020.
4. Shuhrat Sirojiddinov Program and methodical manual for studying the life and work of Alexander Arkadievich Feinberg